

FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH BEHAVIOR OF SiC-REINFORCED ALUMINUM-ALLOY COMPOSITES IN AGGRESSIVE ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Two aluminum-based (6061, 7090) silicon carbide-reinforced (20 vol.%) composites were studied for fatigue crack growth rate (FCGR) in dry argon, distilled water, and 3.5% NaCl environments. Compact tension specimens were tested at frequencies of 1 Hz and 10 Hz, with load ratio 0.15. Some 6061 specimens tested at low ΔK values showed first a falling, then a rising FCGR, i.e. minimum growth rate like that usually associated with short-crack effects. The 7090 composites did not show minima in FCGR. At low ΔK both alloy systems exhibited progressively higher growth rates in the order: argon, distilled water, salt water. The 7090 composites were more sensitive to salt water than was the 6061 composite. As FCGR increased, crack growth rates became progressively less sensitive to environment and loading frequency. In most environments, increasing the loading frequency increased FCGR, implying that corrosion-induced closure occurs at low ΔK levels.

KEYWORDS: Crack propagation; environment; fatigue; matrix, aluminum; particulate composite

1. INTRODUCTION

Aluminum alloys have a long history of use as aerospace materials. Among the limiting factors in application of these materials, however, are the elastic modulus and, to a lesser extent, the tensile strength. One of the driving forces in development of silicon carbide-reinforced composites with aluminum alloy matrices has been to increase modulus with little weight penalty, thus achieving high stiffness-to-weight ratio. As has been reviewed [1-5], silicon carbide reinforcement has indeed resulted in improvements in yield and ultimate tensile strengths over the respective unreinforced base alloys. Unfortunately, fracture resistance, expressed for example as fracture toughness, is usually significantly degraded by the presence of the reinforcement [2,4-7]. The loss in toughness is typically accompanied by changes in fatigue

crack growth resistance [2,4,7-11]. Particulate composites exhibit good isotropy of properties, and as processing methods have improved [2,12,13], properties have become more consistent.

As with conventional aluminum alloys [14-21], it is also becoming clear that there can be environmentally degrading effects on mechanical properties in aluminum-alloy composites [6,10,22], which may have a variety of origins. Several researchers have suggested possible mechanisms for corrosion fatigue in aluminum alloys [16,19,20,23], including hydrogen embrittlement and slip-dissolution processes, as reviewed elsewhere [18-20,23-26]. Since corrosion fatigue in aqueous solutions involves simultaneous anodic and cathodic processes, it is impossible to separate the two directly, although indirect separations have been attempted [18,20]. However, it is possible to increase the hydrogen concentration, or promote hydrogen charging at the tip of a growing crack, by changing environmental testing conditions.

In the present work, two different aluminum alloy composites were tested in three different environments, each supporting different hydrogen conditions at the crack tip. The environments were chosen to make use of the accelerating affects of chloride ions [17,18,26-29] on corrosion fatigue, and also to examine the effects of cyclic loading frequency variations on fatigue behavior, since these can control the time for an environmental effect to occur.

2. EXPERIMENTS

We investigated the fatigue crack growth rates of two aluminum-based composites, 6061 and 7090. See Table 1 for base compositions.

Table 1. Composition of Aluminum Alloy Composite Matrix Materials

Alloy	Mg	Zn	Si	Cu	Co	Cr	Al	
6061	1.0	--	0.6	0.3	--	0.2	Bal.	(weight percents, nominal)
7090	2.5	8.0	--	1.0	1.5	--	Bal.	

Each alloy, through powder metallurgical techniques, was combined with silicon carbide particles, such that the final composite contained 20 volume percent SiC. The average diameter of the particles in the 6061 system was 5 μm , while in the 7090 composite the average particle diameter was 2 μm . Particle clustering was somewhat more evident in the 6061 composite, as shown elsewhere [30,31]. Both the 6061 and 7090 composites were produced by DWA Composite Specialties (Chatsworth, California).

The as-received material was heat treated as follows. For the 6061-base material, solution treatment was 1 h at 530°C/WQ (water quench), then aged 6.5 h at 175°C/WQ, which is a T6 condition. In the 7090-base material, the treatment comprised 2 h at 495°C/WQ; 24 h at 120°C/WQ; 3 h at 410°C/furnace cool to 260°C/WQ. The non-standard 7090 heat treatment constituted considerable overaging (in an effort to gain environmental resistance), and resulted in a softened microstructure containing large precipitates [5], as evidenced by its steady-state room temperature hardness value of 60 RH-B (vs. 99 RH-B for 7090-T6). Compact tension

(CT) specimens, proportioned according to ASTM guidelines, were 3.2 mm thick. After heat treatment, tensile and CT specimens were polished with 1- μ m diamond paste.

Room temperature tensile properties for each extruded composite alloy have been reported elsewhere [4,10,12,22,32] and are not repeated here. The results in this paper are for CT specimens fatigue tested in the LT orientation in which the loading direction is parallel to, and the crack growth direction is transverse to the final rolling direction. Transverse specimen results have been presented elsewhere [30]. All CT specimens were fatigue precracked in laboratory air at 10 Hz or less. Cracks were grown to the appropriate precrack length (6 mm or more), recommended by ASTM-E647-81, and were measured using a 20X-traveling microscope with precision to 0.013 mm. Specimens were thin enough to permit visual crack monitoring from only one side, per ASTM guideline. In all but one case [30], crack lengths were measured *in situ*. For all fatigue cracking and pre-cracking, the load ratio $R = P_{\min}/P_{\max} = 0.15$. Load shedding decreased ΔK during the precracking period until ΔK_{th} was reached, then measurement was begun using P_{\max} and P_{\min} of ΔK_{th} , and these loads were not changed for the duration of the test. Some CT specimens of 6061 were stored in laboratory air for as long as 20 days before testing.

Each composite was tested in three environments: dry argon, distilled water, and 3.5% NaCl in water at a fatigue frequency of either 1 or 10 Hz. The specimen designation system for these tests comprised symbols for the environment (A = argon, W = distilled water, S = salt water), orientation (T = transverse crack growth direction, i.e. longitudinally loaded), and loading frequency (1 or 10, frequency in Hz). Thus "AT-10" designates an argon test at 10 Hz.

Environmental testing was conducted in an enclosed testing chamber, as shown previously [30]. For argon testing, the argon was dried, and relative humidity monitored with a hygrometer. For aqueous environments, test solutions were aerated and circulated through the environmental chamber. Distilled water pH at the crack tip was taken to be 3.5 [18,27,28]. The temperature of all aqueous solutions was $25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. Open circuit potentials of specimens immersed in test solutions were measured relative to a saturated calomel electrode, connected to the environmental chamber by a salt bridge [30].

Fatigue crack growth rates were calculated using the secant method as described in ASTM-E647-81. Fatigue crack growth rate (FCGR) data presented in this paper are plotted on log/linear scales, where the individual contributions of environmental and mechanical (loading frequency) effects are most readily distinguishable.

3. RESULTS

3.1 6061 Composites The effects of environment on the FCGR of 6061 composites is shown in Figure 1. At low ΔK ($< 8.7 \text{ MPa } \sqrt{\text{m}}$), the environmental severity has little effect on FCGR, as shown by very similar growth rates in distilled and salt water solutions. However, environmental FCGR, distilled or salt water, is distinctly faster than in the inert argon atmosphere. This pattern of results has been observed before for 6061 composites [10]. The data for aqueous environments converge with those for argon at 9 to 10 $\text{MPa } \sqrt{\text{m}}$. Beyond that

point, predominantly mechanical effects appear to control FCGR, as we have discussed elsewhere [30]. In what follows, we focus on the behavior at low growth rates, i.e. below 9 or 10 MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$, since that appears to provide the maximum environmental effects of interest.

Figure 1. Fatigue of 6061 composites at 10 Hz, all three environments.

As we have shown previously [30], there is a difference in the fracture surface appearance for the 6061 composites. The argon fracture surface was uncorroded and was characterized by high relief and distinctive features, primarily blocky, ductile tear ridges and microvoids, while that of the salt water or ST test showed abundant corrosion products and less surface relief. This immediately suggests two possible effects of environment on FCGR in these tests: changes in crack closure [33-35] due to changes in fracture roughness or in corrosion product thickness.

Although crack closure effects are typically observed at low ΔK levels [33-35], Fig. 1 may also indicate time-dependent corrosion buildup at mid- ΔK levels. This is in addition to any closure effect at low ΔK levels. However, we have done no tests, e.g. at higher R values, to verify that corrosion-assisted closure persists in salt water above the mid- ΔK range.

The data for FCGR at 10 Hz below $\Delta K = 6.5$ MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$ in the distilled water test were omitted from Figure 1. Those data are presented in Figure 2 as a dashed line. It is immediately evident that this curve (and also the data for 1 Hz, described below) shows decreasing FCGR as ΔK increases at the lowest ΔK values, followed by an increase, with the minimum rate at about $\Delta K = 6.5$ MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$. This is classical evidence of a crack closure effect, at least when cracks are small [34-41]. The present data, however, are for through-thickness cracks in compact tension specimens, precracked to 6 mm or greater length, and thus these cracks cannot be considered to be small [34]. This behavior is discussed below.

It was noted above that in Figure 1, the expected relationship of the FCGR's for the various environments was obtained; but notice in Figure 2 that the expected behavior with frequency was not observed for $\Delta K < 8$ MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$. Here, the longer exposure time per cycle has resulted in slower, not faster, FCGR. Such a result appears contradictory to conventional electrochemical

approaches, whether emphasizing hydrogen or slip dissolution effects [20,26], since such approaches would predict the opposite behavior in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Fatigue crack growth of 6061 composites in distilled water, 1 Hz vs. 10 Hz. Specimen storage times shown next to curves.

Conventionally, if hydrogen generated from water reacting with aluminum were the cause of the effects on FCGR, the 1 Hz frequency would provide more time for hydrogen generation; similarly, if specimen storage time (leading to hydrogen pick-up from laboratory humidity) were the primary factor influencing FCGR, a longer storage time should cause higher growth rates. But these data corroborate neither hypothesis, since the FCGR at 10 Hz is faster than at 1 Hz. The environmental effect in Fig. 2 is clearly such as to retard crack growth, and increases in crack closure seem the likeliest reason. Note also that at ΔK values above about 7.5 MPa \sqrt{m} , the effect of cyclic frequency appears to vanish. The effect of frequency in Fig. 2 is discussed further in section 4, below.

Fatigue testing results in salt water are shown in Figure 3. Although the differences between 1 Hz and 10 Hz appear small here, that appearance is partly an artifact of different FCGR scales in the two figures. It can also be noted that there is a minimum growth rate exhibited by the data for 1 Hz. This figure might be interpreted as the classical rate effect, if salt water is causing corrosion fatigue and affecting the growth rate, since 1 Hz FCGR exceeded that for 10 Hz, but closure effects must also be considered, and are discussed below.

Fractographic examination of specimens fatigued in salt water showed [30] at low ΔK that SiC particles cleanly decohered from the aluminum alloy matrix and were prominent on the fracture surface. By contrast, at higher ΔK values such as 12 MPa \sqrt{m} , the generally blocky, tear-ridge topography contained microvoids like those seen for the argon tests, though significant amounts of corrosion products were found on all aqueous fracture surfaces.

Figure 3. Fatigue cracking of 6061 composites in salt water, 10 Hz vs. 1 Hz. Specimen storage times shown by curves.

3.2 7090 Composites Testing of the 7090 composites at 10 Hz gave the results shown in Figure 4. For this alloy matrix, FCGR behavior appears independent of environment at high ΔK ; SiC particles do not influence the fatigue-fracture behavior significantly in this ΔK region [42]. At low ΔK levels, though, FCGR behavior is very environment-sensitive. The FCGR in water is more than twice that in argon, and FCGR in salt water is more than four times the argon rate. These data reflect more classical behavior than do the results for the 6061 composite, in that growth rates are ranked by environment "severity" at low ΔK . The qualitative idea that severity increases from argon to distilled water to salt water is borne out by measurements of specimen electrochemical potentials measured during testing [30].

Figure 4. Fatigue of 7090 composites at 10 Hz, all three environments.

Figure 5. Fatigue crack growth of 7090 composites, 10 Hz vs. 1 Hz, in distilled water.

Turning to the details of behavior in 7090, it appears that at mid-to-high ΔK , cyclic frequency in distilled water has little if any effect on FCGR in 7090, as shown in Figure 5. At low ΔK , though, lower frequency resulted in slightly lower FCGR in this composite, again probably due to closure effects. There is at most a modest minimum in FCGR at 1 Hz in the 7090 data shown in Figure 5. No 7090 specimens were stored in lab air prior to test.

Figure 6. Fatigue of 7090 composites in salt water, 10 Hz vs. 1 Hz.

In salt water, FCGR behavior for 1 and 10 Hz frequencies was more dramatic than in the distilled water environment. At low ΔK levels, the FCGR at 10 Hz exceeded that at 1 Hz by a factor of about two, as Figure 6 illustrates; the FCGR at 1 Hz is slightly faster than FCGR in

distilled water, Fig. 5. Here again, closure likely is affecting the FCGR behavior. The effect, however, is not such as to cause a minimum in FCGR at low ΔK values. Unfortunately, the aqueous environments were so corrosive to the 7090 composites that no fractography was possible, even after surface cleaning. Thus no observation of fracture surface roughness could be made, and interpretations of 7090 results must rely on mechanical measurements alone.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 6061 Composites At most ΔK levels for this composite, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) profile fractographs [30,31,43] indicated that SiC particles participate in the fracture process primarily by separating from the matrix in one of two modes. Separation either occurs between SiC particles and the matrix at the interface (decohesion), or a small layer of aluminum alloy remains adhered to the SiC particles, i.e., separation takes place near but not at the SiC/Al matrix interface. Both separation types were observed, as in prior work on 2124-matrix composites [6,43]. In general, SiC particles in 6061 tended to separate rather than crack during fatigue fracture, and apparently few particles were cracked during processing, since frequencies of cracked particles were low and about the same in tested and untested specimens [31]. Enhanced particle separation and microvoiding at low ΔK , as found for 6061, could enhance surface roughness, on the scale of a few micrometers [44,45].

At low ΔK levels, aqueous tests exhibited similar behavior; FCGR for both was higher than in argon. This aqueous effect decreased as FCGR (and ΔK) increased. Although at low ΔK values the 6061 composite is sensitive to aqueous environments, it is relatively insensitive to the specimen's potential [30], i.e., salt water vs. distilled water. As mentioned, corrosion products formed in aqueous environments may contribute to crack closure. At some mid- ΔK level, though, all three growth rates converged, suggesting that the rate-controlling mechanism at low ΔK becomes dominated by macroscopic, mechanical effects. Since the load ratio is relatively low, the high- ΔK behavior in salt water may be due to corrosion buildup and subsequent corrosion-induced closure, though additional tests to explore this behavior are needed.

One possibility for the minimum in FCGR at low ΔK for the distilled water specimens is hydrogen effects, generated either from the test environment or from storage in laboratory air prior to fatigue testing. Hydrogen, a reaction product of aluminum with either water or humid-air moisture (subcritical cracks can grow in aluminum alloys exposed to water vapor [18,46,47]), may diffuse ahead of the crack tip and become trapped at the SiC/Al interface. The effects of hydrogen trapped at particles have been identified in previous work [47-51]. Crack growth behavior in distilled water tests would then be interpreted as having a minimum in FCGR because the crack first grew in a hydrogen-embrittled region at rates above those characteristic of threshold behavior [33] without hydrogen, then decreased as the crack grew through regions in the matrix containing progressively less entrapped hydrogen, and as corrosion-induced closure developed.

At intermediate ΔK levels (about $6.35 \text{ MPa } \sqrt{\text{m}}$), FCGR assumed a normal increase with ΔK . In this region of slow crack advance, lower cyclic frequency results in lower growth rates. This

non-classical corrosion fatigue behavior evidently arose because the 1 Hz specimen's total immersion time in the aqueous environment was sufficient to allow corrosion product buildup on the crack surface, which lowered FCGR. Corrosion closure is favored here because crack growth was slower, not faster, with 20 days storage vs. 7 days, and was slower at slower frequency despite more time for hydrogen generation.

In salt water, it is again possible that hydrogen affected FCGR at 1 Hz, since a slight minimum in growth rate was found. This effect, however, was smaller than with distilled water. The presence of chloride ions should assist hydrogen generation by corrosion reactions [18,27], thus accelerating FCGR at the lower frequency. Thus any corrosion-induced closure is apparently dominated by hydrogen acceleration of the crack growth mechanism.

4.2 7090 Composites These composites appear to be more sensitive than the 6061 composites to distilled and salt water solutions, perhaps due to the presence of zinc in the base (7090) alloy. They also form thicker corrosion product films at the testing frequencies used in these tests.

Considering all three environments together, as in Fig. 4, it is evident that for low ΔK levels FCGR is very sensitive to environment. In distilled water, hydrogen concentration at the crack tip may control FCGR, whereas in the salt solution, the cathodic reaction may be rate limiting [18,20,28,48]. At mid-to-high ΔK , environmental effects diminished; like the 6061 composites, FCGR curves for all three environments converged. However, unlike the 6061 alloy, there is a large difference in FCGR at low ΔK levels between WT and ST. If more hydrogen is present at the crack tip, transport of hydrogen into the plastic zone by mobile dislocations perhaps is occurring, as claimed in other aluminum alloys [48-50,52]. This hypothesis could account for the direct proportionality between FCGR and potential [30] at low ΔK levels in 7090.

In distilled water at all ΔK levels, the 7090 composite is fairly insensitive to frequency, with possibly a small closure effect at 1 Hz. In salt water at low-to-mid ΔK , lower loading frequency results in lower FCGR. These data indicate that even when the 7090 composite is subjected to an aggressive environment for prolonged times (i.e. 1 Hz in salt water), cracks grow more slowly than if the composite had been fatigued at 10 Hz. The explanation probably involves corrosion product buildup and increased crack closure, due to longer immersion time (1 Hz), which lowers the 1 Hz growth rate, or possibly to a balance between hydrogen acceleration of FCGR, and corrosion-induced closure deceleration of FCGR. More testing would be needed to separate these possibilities.

4.3 Crack closure effects The explanation advanced above for the environmental effects on FCGR in the composite materials of this study is based on crack closure. Using the relation [33,53,54] for maximum CTOD (crack tip opening displacement) at threshold, $CTOD = 0.49 (K_{max})^2 / (YE)$, where Y = yield strength, E = Young's modulus (published [3] for 20% SiC composites), and K_{max} is the maximum stress intensity at threshold, the CTOD values for 6061 near the apparent threshold of about $\Delta K = 6 \text{ MPa} \sqrt{\text{m}}$ are about $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. This is smaller than the scale of fractographic features associated with voiding around the $5\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ SiC in 6061, and is also smaller than the corrosion thickness formed, since that product can obscure $1\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ fractographic

features, especially in salt water environments. Thus either changes in local roughness through environmentally-induced changes in fracture micromechanisms, or the formation of corrosion products, can affect crack mechanics [33,37,54,55]. Water environments certainly result in corrosion products (and concomitant hydrogen production), and salt water accelerates this corrosion, in part by penetrating any potentially protective films. It is concluded that corrosion-induced closure is apparently dominant in distilled water, Figs. 2 and 5, while the chloride penetration of the corrosion appears to assist hydrogen micromechanisms which increase local roughness in salt water, Figs. 3 and 6. More detailed experiments to explore these possibilities, as well as electrochemical measurements to permit comparison to models [20,26], are clearly needed before a more complete explanation can be provided.

5. CONCLUSIONS

For the 6061 composites, FCGR appears to be sensitive to aqueous environments, compared to argon, but not necessarily to the specimen potential, i.e. distilled vs. salt water. At some mid- ΔK level, though, growth rates in all three environments converge. The behavior in salt water at mid-to-high ΔK may be due to corrosion-assisted closure. The data do not support either classical electrochemical hypotheses for FCGR acceleration, nor damage from pre-test hydrogen ingress. It appears likely that corrosion-induced closure is responsible. In salt water, an opposite effect of frequency to that in distilled water was found, possibly due to a balance between hydrogen and corrosion-induced closure effects on FCGR.

For 7090 composites, a marked environmental effect of FCGR was found at low ΔK levels, but at higher ΔK , FCGR converged in all three environments. However, unlike the 6061, there is a large difference in FCGR at low ΔK levels between salt and distilled water. Frequency effects were not detected in distilled water, but in salt water at low-to-mid ΔK , 10-Hz FCGR was greater than at 1 Hz. The explanation may involve corrosion-induced closure.

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